

Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* Isolated from Chicken Liver and Trachea

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ABSTRACT

Escherichia coli is a poultry bacterial pathogen reported for causing a wide variety of disease. The aim of this research was to determine the antibiotic susceptibility of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* isolated from liver and trachea of freshly dead chicken. Ninety seven (97) freshly dead chicken from 23 different farms where analyzed for the presence of pathogenic *E. coli*. In vitro susceptibility of the isolates against antimicrobial agents was determined using disk diffusion method. A total of forty eight (48) pathogenic *E. coli* were isolated, twenty one (21) of the isolates were recovered from the chicken trachea while twenty seven (27) were from the liver. A total of 43 out of the 48 isolated *E. coli* showed haemolysis on sheep blood agar, which constituted 89.6% of the entire *E. coli*. The overall resistant pattern of the isolated *E. coli* showed that Nitrofurantoin (NIT 300 µg) had the best antimicrobial activity with resistance of 20.8%. Ampicillin (AMP 10 µg) was most resisted with 89.6 % of the *E. coli* forming resistance. The resistant of other antibiotic used are Ceftazidime (CAZ 30 µg) 45.8%, Cefuroxime (CRX 30 µg) 60.4%, Gentamicin (GEN 10 µg) 68.8%, Ciprofloxacin (CPR 5 µg) 47.9%, Ofloxacin (OFL 5 µg) 52.1%, and Amoxicillin/Clavulinate (AUG 30 µg) 79.2%.

Keyword: *Escherichia coli*, Haemolysis, Liver, Trachea, Antibiogram.

INTRODUCTION:

Escherichia coli is one of the most important and frequently encountered bacterial avian pathogen causing a wide variety of disease and syndromes in birds, which are of significant concern to the poultry industry [9]. *E. coli* had been repeatedly incriminated in disease and syndromes like Colibacillosis which is a common systemic infection in poultry, colisepticaemia in chicks, acute enteritis, airsacculitis, pericarditis, peritonitis, coligranuloma of liver, synovitis, swollen-head syndrome and osteomyelitis [2, 22, 23]. These diseases caused considerable economic damage to poultry production worldwide [15]. The extensive use of antibiotics for bacterial infections in human and veterinary Medicine had resulted in a great trend of resistance in microorganisms. The resistant gene can also be transfer to other bacteria of the same or other species thereby further enhancing the spread of such gene [14, 16].

Antibiotics are used in livestock feed at sub-therapeutic doses to promote growth and increase feed efficiency. However, the use of antibiotics in animals is not totally safe. One of the main concerns is the development of antibiotic resistant bacteria [13]. In poultry and pig production, misuse of antibiotics had resulted in the development and maintenance of populations of antibiotic-resistant organisms. The emergence and spread of resistant bacterial strains like *Campylobacter* spp., *Escherichia coli* and *Enterococcus* sp in the intestinal tracts of these animals, making them reservoirs for resistant bacteria [9, 4]. Significant increase in emergence of drug-resistant strains of *E. coli* isolated from poultry had been reported. [1, 9, 10, 19].

Food of animal origin may serve as a vehicle to transport resistant bacteria and resistance genes between animals and humans since

contamination of carcasses with faecal flora inevitably occurs during slaughtering [27]. In addition to the human health concerns, antimicrobial-resistant pathogens also pose a severe and costly animal health problem, as they prolong illness and decrease productivity through higher morbidity and mortality rate [6]. In this study, *E. coli* isolated from the liver and trachea of freshly dead chicken were subjected to antimicrobial agents in order to determine their resistant level.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials

Ninety seven (97) freshly dead chicken were brought from 23 different farms in Ondo and Ekiti State to Metrovet Veterinary hospital Ado Ekiti for diagnosis between January and June 2015.

Necropsy

The Freshly dead chicken were necropsied, the liver and trachea were collected. Swabs were collected aseptically from the trachea and the liver for bacteria isolation.

Bacteriology

The swabs collected from both the liver and the trachea were activated in buffered peptone water for 1hour at 37 °C. A loop full of the activated organisms in the buffered peptone water were inoculated onto MacConkey agar (Biomark) and Sorbitol MacConkey Agar (Biomark) by streaking. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours in an incubator (Royalcare England. DNP 9022A).

Hemolysis.

Overnight bacterial cultures were streaked on sheep blood agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The appearance of a zone of

erythrocyte lysis around or under bacterial colonies indicated hemolysis.

Biochemical

Further confirmation was done by Gram reaction, motility, catalase, oxidase, H₂S production, Nitrate, urease, indole, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, and citrate use tests [8]. The *E. coli* isolates were selected based on colony morphology and biochemical tests.

Antimicrobial Drug Sensitivity Test.

In vitro susceptibility of the isolates against antimicrobial agents was determined by the standard disk diffusion procedure [5]. The organisms were standardized using McFarland standard at the absorbance of 450nm. The samples were inoculated on Muller-Hinton agar. The following antimicrobial agents were tested: Ceftazidime (CAZ 30 µg), Cefuroxime (CRX 30 µg), Gentamicin (GEN 10 µg), Ciprofloxacin (CPR 5 µg), Ofloxacin (OFL 5 µg), Nitrofurantoin (NIT 300 µg), Ampicillin (AMP 10 µg), and Amoxicillin/Clavulinate (AUG 30 µg). Following the application of antimicrobial discs, the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h in an incubator (Royalcare England. DNP 9022A). The diameters of the zones of inhibition were measured (millimetres) and were compared to internationally accepted standard to determine the susceptibility or resistance of the isolate [21].

RESULT

Pure colonies of bacteria were isolated in MacConkey agar plates from all the samples. All isolates were identified as *E. coli* based on morphological and biochemical characteristics. All *E. coli* isolated were round convex colonies and ferment lactose to give a pink coloration on the MacConkey agar. The biochemical test is presented in table 1. A total of forty eight (48) *Escherichia coli* were found to be pathogenic based on their inability to ferment sorbitol. Twenty one (21) pathogenic *E. coli* isolates were recovered from the trachea of the dead chicken, while 27

pathogenic *E. coli* isolates were recovered from the liver of the dead chicken.

Twenty five (25) out of 27 of the pathogenic *E. coli* isolated from the chicken liver showed haemolysis, this value constituted 92.6 % of the isolates. The isolates from the trachea also showed haemolysis with 18 out of 21 being haemolytic, which constituted 85.7 % of the pathogenic *E. coli*. A total of 89.6% of the entire pathogenic *E. coli* can were found to be haemolytic.

Table1: Biochemical reaction of the isolates.

Biochemical reactions	Result
Gram Reaction	-
Motility	+
Catalase	+
Oxidase	-
Indole	+
Methyl-Red	+
Voges-Proskauer	-
Citrate	-
H ₂ S production	-
Nitrate	+
Urease	-

Key: + positive; - negative

The antibiogram showed that 92.6% of the *E. coli* recovered from the liver are resistant to ampicillin and 88.9% were resistant to Amoxicillin/Clavulinate, 85.7% of *E. coli* from trachea were resistant to ampicillin and 76.1% were resistant to Ofloxacin. Nitrofurantoin was found to be least resisted by isolates from liver and trachea with resistance value of 14.8% and 28.6% respectively. The average resistant pattern of the Pathogenic *E. coli* showed that ampicillin is most resisted with a value of 89.6% followed by Amoxicillin/Clavulinate with a value of 79.2%. Nitrofurantoin had an average resistant value of 20.8% (table 2).

Table 2: Antibiotic resistance pattern of isolate in percentages (%)

Isolates	CAZ	CRX	GEN	CPR	OFL	NIT	AMP	AUG
Liver (n=27)	48.1	63.0	55.6	29.6	33.3	14.8	92.6	88.9
Trachea (n=21)	42.8	57.1	85.7	71.4	76.1	28.6	85.7	66.7
Total (n=48)	45.8	60.4	68.8	47.9	52.1	20.8	89.6	79.2

Ceftazidime (CAZ 30 µg), Cefuroxime (CRX 30 µg), Gentamicin (GEN 10 µg), Ciprofloxacin (CPR 5 µg), Ofloxacin (OFL 5 µg), Nitrofurantoin (NIT 300 µg), Ampicillin (AMP 10 µg), and Amoxicillin/Clavulinate (AUG 30 µg).

DISCUSSION

Escherichia coli were found to be responsible for high early chick mortality and reduced hatchability [24]. Isolating *E. coli* from the chicken liver had been reported [17]. Huff *et al.* (2002) [12] had earlier reported that *E. coli* caused respiratory infections in poultry and could be recovered from the trachea. The *E. coli* isolate in this study are basically pathogenic *E. coli* based on their inability to ferment sorbitol and the heamolitic effect. Generally, *E. coli* had been isolated from other part of chicken which include the yolk sac and the intestine, however they are most prominent in the liver of infected birds [24].

Modestas *et al.* (2010) [17] reported that *E. coli* isolated from liver of chicken had a resistance of 47% to ciprofloxacin and 60% to ampicillin, this result is also in line with what was observed for ciprofloxacin with 47.9% and ampicillin 89.6 % in this research. The highest sensitivity was recorded for Nitrofurantoin with only 20.8% of the *E. coli* isolates being resistant. This result is similar

to what Roy *et al.* (2006) [24] observed for *E. coli* isolated from Quail birds, where Nitrofurantoin was found to be most sensitive of the antibiotic used, followed by Gentamicin and Ciprofloxacin. However in this research the trend was Nitrofurantoin, Ceftazidime and Ciprofloxacin. The high sensitivity of the isolated organisms to Nitrofurantoin, Ceftazidime and Ciprofloxacin could be related to less frequent usage of these drugs for therapeutic purposes, therefore reducing the chance of resistance to develop [18].

The major factors responsible for antimicrobial resistance in bacteria is antibiotic misuse, crowding and poor sanitation. These three factors are typical of intensive poultry farming and explain the high prevalence and degree of resistance in *E. coli* of poultry origin [27]. The *E. coli* isolates in this study showed high resistance to multiple drugs, they were resistant to at least three antibiotics. The source of the resistance may have come from the poultry feeds consumed, since antibiotics are used as feed

additives to improve feed efficiency and weight gain [11, 26]. Many antibiotics are also used in feed and water to control disease. Indiscriminate use of antibiotics has provided selective pressure for the emergence of drug resistant strains of bacteria associated with poultry products [7, 20, 25].

The use of antibiotics in feed may have provided selective pressure resulting in a larger proportion of *E. coli* resistance. As reported by Atere *et al.* (2015) [3] poultry feeds are main source of infection in chicken in which most of the pathogenic microorganisms including *Salmonella* sp and *E. coli* were found. The United States Food and Drug Administration emphasizes the spread of drug resistance in the enterobacteriaceae family from antibiotic-fed animals to human beings [26]. Transmission of the R-plasmid from *E. coli* of poultry to human occurs very commonly [28]. This makes antibiotic resistance a public health issue.

Poultry feed was not only source of pathogen in poultry birds. Roy *et al.* (2006) [24] had earlier reported that *Escherichia coli* isolates cultured from Japanese quail infected with colibacillosis were the same serotype predominant in the hatchery environment. This is an indication that proper hygiene can assist in reducing and controlling *E. coli* infection in poultry birds. The *E. coli* isolates in this study were resistant to many antibiotics and caused mortality in Chicken, it is therefore imperative for poultry farmers to be cautious of the contaminations through the poultry feed and environment.

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